

Factors Affecting Uptake of Formal Financial Services by Small and Medium Entrepreneurs Inkajiado County, Kenya

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Florence Ndunge Mutua-MBA student, Business School, Africa Nazarene University, email: fndungeus@yahoo.com ⁽²⁾ Dr. Charles W. Weda-Lecturer, Business School, Africa Nazarene University

Abstract:

The main purpose of the paper was to determine factors that affect uptake of formal financial services by small and medium entrepreneurs in Kajiado County. The study adopted descriptive survey design and used both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Target population for the study was 2,795, small and medium entrepreneurs registered in the five sub-counties within Kajiado County. Sample size was arrived at through stratified and simple random techniques. From the target population of 2,795, a sample size of 280 was used for the study. Primary data was collected through questionnaires and structured interviews. From the questionnaires administered 252 were completed culminating into 90% response rate. Data collected was analyzed using Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis and presented using frequency tables. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for analysis. The study found out that among the four variables studied, that is; collateral requirement and level of financial literacy are the main factor that hindered the uptake of the formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado county. The study was of importance to county governments and financial institutions in Kenya in understanding the factors affecting the uptake of formal financial services by small and medium entrepreneurs. It was also of great help to county potential investors in making informed decisions of whether or not to invest in the counties. The study was also of great help to other researchers who hope to increase the body of knowledge in this important field of formal financial services.

Keywords: Collateral Requirement, Level Of Financial Literacy, Uptake Of The Formal Financial Services And Small And Medium Entrepreneurs

Introduction

The contribution of microfinance to entrepreneurship activities is increasingly being recognized as a primary engine to economic growth (Anyanwu, 2006). Through the combination of the available resources and innovative ideas, the small and medium entrepreneurs are able to add value by creating new jobs, commercializing of new products and building of new firms. It has been established by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) that the nations which enjoy high level entrepreneurship have very strong economic growth. From this assertion, it is evident that the link between the new ideas and economic development are entrepreneurs. Legislative actions have been taken by countries like United States of America, the Netherlands and Japan to see to the fact that entrepreneurial activities can contribute to economic development. Various governments around the world have promoted entrepreneurial skills and strategies to tackle different social problems, addressing poverty and employing the disadvantaged (Anyanwu, 2006).

In a conference termed "Improving Access to Microfinance", Soludo(2008) exhibited that in order to achieve sustainability within the increased participation of the skilled entrepreneurs both in the credit and financial service delivery, it was important that the micro, small and medium enterprises through the micro finance sector develop articulate and well-focused entrepreneurs through setting up of the Entrepreneurship Development Centers. He further added that the economically active but poor and low income earners access to microfinance services should be a collective responsibility for the achievement Sustainable Development Goals. This provides a strong focus on macro-economic stabilization, especially in pursuance of massive trades and investment programs to encourage entrepreneurial capacity, to develop business and for the business success (Soludo, 2008).

Researchers and scholars have recognized the crucial role that entrepreneurship plays in economic development of nations, especially through development of micro finance subsector (Ebiringa, 2011). According to Dozie (2007), the bedrock to any nation's industrialization and development is actually the vital factor of production which will form the basis of the Schumpeter's dynamism. He added that this can however be realized through innovative ideas and the ability to take risks by the entrepreneurs. It is therefore, the entrepreneur who generates

the crucial momentum that an economy requires for economic growth by breaking new grounds in human endeavor as a result of vital characteristics they possess (Ebiringa, 2011).

The growth and performance of enterprise is dependent upon the aspect of business financing. According to Shepherd, McMullen & Jennings (2007), the most difficult situation in the operation of new business and especially the small business enterprises is the acquisition of business finance. It is important to note that the availability of finance options to a given entrepreneur is determined by a number of factors among them the perspective of debt and equity and by the use of other external funds. Manasseh (2004) defines external finances or rather the credit finances as the type of finances that are obtained from other sources other than the real owner of the business. This meant the creditors to the given organization. Further, it was added that the credit facilities given can take any of the following forms; lease finance, overdrafts, trade creditors, loan debentures amongst others. The growth and development of an enterprise may be affected by its capital base. This capital will depend on two main sources which are the own sources of capital and the borrowed sources of capital. Nevertheless, the portion of finance that normally depends on credit may not be available to the small and medium level traders. The factors affecting availability of financial services to small traders will be looked at in this study and they include; interest rate, literacy levels, number of lending institutions and the security for the facilities (Manasseh, 2004).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is an important sub sector for the Kenyan economy like many other developing countries since it employs about 85% of the Kenyan workforce. Despite their dedicated efforts of contributing positively to the growth of their economies, it has emerged that majority of them have been sidelined when it comes to accessing formal financial services. Nevertheless, the greatest hindrance to the success and growth of the small and medium entrepreneurs has been due to capital constraints.

According to Littlefield and Rosenberg (2004), the poor are generally excluded from the financial services sector of the economy. MFIs therefore emerged as an instrument to address this market failure. Lack of access to credit has been rated as a major and challenging factor facing SMEs due to their informal nature and their lack of collateral (GOK Survey, 2006); Ministry of Planning and National Development. The government has been adopting monetary, fiscal and industrial development policies and certain measures within the macro level sectors in order to enhance and facilitate entrepreneurship activities while at the same time finance arrangements are being made in respect of funding programs at micro level to boost entrepreneurial activities.

According to Aleke (2001), many MSEs use savings and loans by family members and friends because they cannot access funds from the country's financial system, besides several financial infrastructure limitations which include inconsistent government policy on interest rate and unmet credit needs among others. Wanjohi and Mugure (2008) observed that many SMEs use affordable inappropriate technologies as they lack collateral to access credit to advance their technology. Business growth is predicated upon many factors; among this is the ability of entrepreneurs to access financial services. Furthermore, it has been established that ninety percent of micro and small businesses collapse in their first year of startup due to lack of financial resources (K'Obonyo, 2001). In as much as many financial institutions have been marketing their facilities vigorously; the uptake of the same by entrepreneurs has been minimal (Gichuai, 2014). It has however, not been established comprehensively as to why young and upcoming entrepreneurs tend to shy away from formal financial lending services. Research on various entrepreneurial development aspects have been conducted, but of concern is that one of the main challenges faced by upcoming small and medium entrepreneurs to date is lack of access to financial facilities. With this in mind it shows that research on factors affecting uptake of formal financial services has not been done and hence the need for research in this area. Therefore, the researcher sought to assess factors that affect uptake of formal financial services by small and medium entrepreneurs in Kajiado County. the study seek to answer the following questions.

- i. How do interest rates charged affect the uptake of formal financial services by small and medium entrepreneurs in Kajiado County?

- ii. How does level of financial literacy affect the uptake of financial services by small entrepreneurs in Kajiado County?

Conceptual Framework

In this study the independent variables included; interest rates charged by banks, financial literacy among entrepreneurs, collateral needed at time of borrowing and the number of lending institutions. On the other hand, a dependent variable is the variable being measured or tested by the researcher (Dodge&McKeough, 2003). It is influenced by being randomly assigned to an experimental or control condition. In our case, the dependent variable is the uptake of formal financial services by small and medium entrepreneurs in Kajiado County.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: (Researcher, 2017)

Theoretical Literature Review

This study anchored its arguments on credit rationing theory. The theory of the credit rationing according to Stiglitz and Weiss (2006) alleges that financial institutions experience this scenario when they are actually faced with a huge deficit contrary to their normal financial expectations. A number of factors are directly responsible for the non-monotonic relationship that would exist between the expected returns and the rise in interest rates. These factors among others include: interest rates failing to screen the borrowers with capability from those without similar capability. By this it means the borrowers who are able to examine their projects and still remain focused within the brackets of the project parameters. The theory continues to point out that the borrowers whose projects become safe in the long run are supposed to jet of the market as soon as the interests' rates are much above the expected outcomes. Many of the financial institutions are aware that going for loan that attract high interest rates is riskier to the borrowers and could have long term effect on their progress. Still within the same breadth Stiglitz and Weiss argue that a considerable increase in the interest rates normally shifts the choice of the borrowers to much riskier projects than before an aspect that still places the financial institutions expected returns at a state of limbo.

Stiglitz and Weiss (2006)& Modigliani and Miller(2009), have together defined the concept of credit theory rationing as the scenario whereby there is an expected excess in the demand for commercial loans at certain prevailing commercial loan interest. Keiding (2013) contends that the financial institutions are in most cases private entities which are propelled into business by the aspect profit maximization. In contrast to the above allegation, not all the individuals or the business organizations which apply for the loans are guaranteed.

Majority of them fail to obtain them due to number of reasons. Some of the individuals or the said organizations may be denied the credit if they are out to charge high interest rates.

According to De Meza and Webb (2012), the credit market is not actually like the normal market that portrays an equivalent between the demand and supply. Borrowers with very exorbitant interest rates often find it difficult to make repayments. Hodgman (2006) proposes that the situation arise because the borrower is unable to pay back the loan owing to its increased interest rates. This results in a scenario where the cost of borrowing becomes higher than the return on the overall investment. This view however was abandoned with time when Stiglitz and Weiss developed an explanation that better expounded on relationship between the credits rationing to the available information asymmetry that exists within the market.

In order to cushion some organizations on the emergence of foreseeable risks, many of the financial institutions perform credit rationing. Sometimes these institutions are not able to control the risks due to aspects of free principles being followed and therefore they decide to conduct the ration on credit in as much as the borrowers (entrepreneurs from Kajiado County) who demand funds are willing to pay higher interest rates (Keiding, 2013). This is in actual sense an example market failure or rather market imperfection whereby the price mechanism aspect fails to realize equilibrium in the market. This imperfection is often attributed to the lack of equilibrium despite the availability of willing borrowers. With respect to such prevailing market interest rates the demand will normally exceed the supply and many of the lenders are reluctant to give out funds or rather increase the interest rates they charge since their profits are at maximum. Thus, creating a link to the information asymmetry, that tends to exist between the lender and the borrower (Keiding, 2013). This theory tends to explain the financing gap that may exist within the finance market like the one in Kajiado County.

Empirical Review

Empirical literature review will focus on what previous researchers found out in line with this study's key independent variables; level of financial literacy and collateral. It will also closely look at findings on the dependent variable; uptake of formal financial services.

Level of Financial Literacy

With reference to Muia and Otiende (2004), education is a basic human right and a special tool for achieving the goals of equality, development and peace. It is crucial in changing the status of small entrepreneur's businesses transactions and improving their empowerment. Small entrepreneurs are often prevented from running competitive businesses by their relatively low education and skill levels in the field, which generally limit their access to the various support and credit services (Cutura, 2007). Even when they have access to information on the financial services and market opportunities available to them, they may be less equipped to comprehend it due to low levels of literacy in the field (UNDP, 2007).

Access of information among women entrepreneurs is actually considered a very important aspect both from the provider of the financial services and from the SMEs perspective. Many of the SMEs will usually call for the much-needed information so as to get in touch with a potential supplier of financial resources (Bowen et al., 2009). This information aids them in evaluating the cost of the financial services that are normally being given. The failure to provide the right information regarding the provision of the financial services especially the loan and the charged interest rates by the various institutions giving loans normally hinders the genuine efforts of the women entrepreneurs in the rural areas from accessing these services. Education is one of the factors that impact positively on growth of firms (King & McGrath, 2009).

The lack of knowledge and information regarding financial services and credit processes places small entrepreneurs at a disadvantage. Despite the resources available, from private and public development finance institutions, few small entrepreneurs know about them, their products and how to have access to them (Brown & Galley, 2004). However much the small entrepreneurs may have access to the information regarding financial

services available to them, the ability to process it may still pose a challenging task to them. This is because they are less equipped. Their lower levels of literacy and lack of exposure to businesses hampers their ability to benefit directly from information that is provided in professional language (UNDP, 2007), and to fully understand the conditions of complex financial products available to them (Brown & Galley, 2004).

In line with Cole, Shawn, Thomas and Bilal (2008), they established out from his experimental work that in India and Indonesia, the main predictor of demand for the financial services was financial literacy. He alluded that this aspect is further exemplified by the low training that was evident among the small entrepreneurs. This vice of lack proper education, skills and work experience regarding the financial services among the small entrepreneurs lessened their attractiveness to lenders. Namusonge (2005) alleges that it is entrepreneurial education and training that has been found to have a significance role in the stimulation of entrepreneurship and self-employment among the micro, small and medium entrepreneurs. Equal access to education and equal opportunity in the gaining the skills are necessary for small entrepreneurs to compete in the business industry. The better education a small entrepreneur has the more the ability and wiliness to compete with big enterprises and this leads to increase in their productivity and in turn reduces discrimination against them (Ngunjiri, 2010).

Research shows that small entrepreneur's limited access to financial information challenges their encounter in the establishment and operation of micro enterprises (Suda, 2002). The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) define an information literate person as someone who can understand information on a field of interest. To achieve this mainstreaming business perspective in policy formulation, planning, programming and implementation is imperative. As it is said, knowledge to the poor is power to the poor. Small entrepreneur's general financial literacy creates a situation of dependency on others that can limit individual's prospects for empowerment (Muia & Otiende, 2004).

Most lenders advertise their financial services on the print media. Since the financial literacy levels among the small entrepreneurs are low, they may not access the information. Others may have general literacy but are not well informed, on the effect of credit facilities on business growth, and therefore may fail to ask for the services. The literacy level may therefore be a constraining factor in the accessibility of credit, among small entrepreneurs. Those entrepreneurs with larger stocks of human capital, in terms of education and (or) vocational training, are better placed to adapt their enterprises to constantly changing business environments (King & McGrath, 2009).

Small entrepreneur's lower access to and use of financial services is primarily associated with economic criteria (Zuñiga, 2004) and the presence of gender-based transaction costs. From a broader perspective, reduced participation in credit markets is due to both demand and supply constraints (Zuñiga, 2004). The most common demand-side constraint consists of; collateral requirements, levels of interest rates, low levels of financial literacy not matching with the complexity of formal financial products and do not allow people to perceive related benefits. These factors and many more constitute barriers that prevent entrepreneurs from having access to resources.

Collateral

Small entrepreneurs over the world face a myriad of challenges in starting and learning the operations of any business. This is according to the World Bank report (2014), which further indicates that small entrepreneurs only own one percent of the investments in business industry. Several studies have been conducted on the small entrepreneurs and the access to financial facilities by the Small Enterprises. For example, (Bowen et al., 2009) on their study he termed: "Management of Business Challenges among Small and Micro Enterprises in Nairobi-Kenya" established that the SME's face a quite a number of challenges in their operations amongst them being lack of access to credit, competition from among themselves, insecurity, cheap imports, high interest rates and debt collection.

According to Peninah (2012), although more businesses have become the customers of banks, the overall volume of credit has not necessarily increased. Taken together with a squeeze in demand for their products and high inflation, small businesses are not always eager for larger bank loans at higher interest rates. Small entrepreneurs throughout the world contribute to national agricultural output and family food security; detailed studies from Latin America, South Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa consistently indicate that small entrepreneurs are more likely to be credit constrained due to lack of collateral than established ones of equivalent socio-economic conditions (Fletschner, Guirkinge & Boucher, 2009).

In Kenya, the private sector has over the years considerably contributed to the country's economic growth. It has contributed more than 80% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) in 2013 produced the following statistics regarding the country's economic growth. The service sector contributed 52% of the GDP, industrial sector 16% and agriculture 29%. There have been reports that most of these organizations have been posting high profits in their financial reports for past few years. There is no doubt that blue chip companies are considered successful or top performers. These companies include East African Breweries (EABL), Nation Media Group (NMG), Safaricom Limited and Barclays Bank Kenya among others.

These companies consequently have applied various strategies that other companies have failed to apply. These strategies have encompassed change. The forces of change are frequently the result of some external forces such as increased competition, new legislation or customer expectations (Salemi, 2007). All these changes have contributed to increased competition, performance and overall increase of their share prices. This has been as a result of investing in technology, employees, re-engineering, re-structuring and utilization of other resources in their operations in order to be competitive. Consequently, in the new competitive Kenyan environment, inefficient and uncompetitive firms cannot survive hence changes and new dynamics in the way organizations are managed and run are inevitable in order to ensure that organization maintain a sustainable competitive edge.

In accordance to ILO (2008) nearly all the small and medium enterprise owners in Kenya are women who contribute to 40% of all the small holder farm managers. Nevertheless, they have merely less than 10% of the credit available to them and nearly less than 1% of the credit on agriculture. Small entrepreneurs' access to financial resources is also limited by biased lending practices that emerge when financial institutions in the area consider them smaller, less experienced and therefore less attractive clients, or when institutions lack the knowledge to offer products tailored to small entrepreneurs' preferences and constraints (Fletschner, 2008a). The extent to which institutions reach out to small entrepreneurs, and the conditions under which they do vary noticeably, the micro, small and medium enterprise entrepreneurs are normally at a great disadvantage especially when an institution fails to fund the type of activities they have opted to run due to a number of reasons such as lack of appropriate guarantors for loans, failure to meet a number of prerequisite requirements among other others. Worse is even the fact of the small entrepreneurs being awarded smaller loans for their activities as compared large entrepreneurs who run similar set of activities (Fletschner, 2008a)

Knowledge Gap

The literature available clearly depicts that Small and medium entrepreneurs in the developing countries have contributed greatly in the economic development of their nations. Despite their contribution to the economies it has emerged that they have been sidelined when it comes to accessing formal financial services. The biggest drawback to the success and growth of the small and medium entrepreneurs has been due to capital constraints (Hodgman, 2006). Thus the entire concept of financial accessibility by small and medium entrepreneurs; which captures the aspects of charged interest rates by the formal financial institutions, level of financial literacy by the borrowers, the collateral requirements by the financial institutions and the number of lending institutions ought to be studied at in-depth to bring out a better understanding of the operational procedures and policies of the financial institutions that would otherwise be useful to the small and medium entrepreneurs in accessing financial services. This will largely improve the rate of uptake of financial services by the small and medium entrepreneurs from the formal financial institutions. The main reason why the small

and medium entrepreneurs will shy away from accessing these financial facilities is the lack of reliable, efficient and effective information to guide them through the application process and the management of the availed financial resources. Consequently, this study is focused on investigating the factors affecting the uptake of formal financial services by the small and medium entrepreneurs in Kajiado County.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive survey design which involved both qualitative and quantitative approaches. This study target population was 2,795 SME traders who were drawn from all the sub-counties in Kajiado County. This study employed both stratified and simple random sampling technique. The researcher used 10% to determine respondents from all the 2,795 small and medium entrepreneurs in the county, this was 280 respondents. The study used questionnaires as the main data collection instrument. The test re-test method was used to assess the reliability of the instruments. Data was summarized using descriptive distribution of scores or measurements using a few indices or statistics and to describe (and compare) variables numerically. Multiple regression analysis was adopted when the researcher had one dependent variable which was assumed to be a function of two or more independent variables.

Findings-Sample Characteristics

From the study, out of the respondents who were interviewed, 138 respondents representing 54.7% were males while 114 respondents that corresponded to 45.3% were females. majority of the respondents were aged 41 -50 years and this represented 38.5% of the sample population. Majority of the respondents had their businesses for duration of 6-7 years which corresponded to 41.7%. 25 respondents had their business in operation for duration of below 2 years which corresponded 9.9%. majority of the respondents had the undergraduate level of education which represented 41.3%. 35 respondents had the primary level of education which was 13.9%. majority of the respondents had employed 1-5 employees in their business.

Descriptive Statistics

Level of Financial Literacy on Uptake of the Formal Financial Services

The respondents were also asked to what extent they agreed or disagreed to the opinion that the Level of Financial Literacy had on the uptake of formal financial services by the SME's in their sub counties. Table 1 shows the results obtained.

Table 2 Level of Financial Literacy on the Uptake of Financial Services

	1	2	3	4	5	Weighted Mean
1 Making informed decisions by small entrepreneurs in Kajiado County is due to their financial literacy	96	39	14	7	82	1
2 The efficiency of managing finances by small and medium entrepreneurs amounts to financial literacy	211	25	5	0	0	1
3 Making informed investments by Kajiado County SMEs is due their financial literacy	67	121	59	0	3	2
4 Good financial literacy by Kajiado SMEs help Manage financial risks effectively	233	19	0	0	0	1
5 Having informed financial literacy skills has help the SMEs in Kajiado County effectively secure their social security funds	248	3	0	0	1	1

From the above data, the findings generated a mean of weighted means of 1 which implies that the respondents strongly agreed to the opinion that indeed the level of financial literacy affects the uptake of the formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County. From these findings, the researcher established that making informed decisions by small entrepreneurs in Kajiado County is due to their level of financial literacy. This was evident from the weighted mean of 1 which implies that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that they make informed decisions based on their level of financial literacy. There was a weighted mean of 1 for the respondents who strongly agreed that the efficiency of managing finances by small and medium entrepreneurs' amounts to financial literacy. This clearly indicated that many of the SME's attain efficiency in their operations due to their level of financial literacy. Respondents who agreed that making informed investments by Kajiado County SMEs is due to their financial literacy had a weighted mean of 2. This was a clear indication to the researcher that majority of the SME's in Kajiado County rely on their financial literacy to make informed investment decisions. Those who strongly felt that good financial literacy by Kajiado SMEs help manage financial risks effectively had a weighted mean of 1; which was an evident declaration for the researcher that indeed the SME's in Kajiado county appreciated the importance of good financial literacy in taking up formal financial services.

The researcher noted a weighted mean of 1 from the respondents on the question of whether having informed financial literacy skills helps the SMEs in Kajiado County effectively secure their social security funds. This implies that ideally all the SME's in Kajiado County were in strong agreement that they needed informed financial literacy in order to assist them in securing the social security funds. Besides, the respondents were asked to specify any other aspects on the level of financial literacy that they thought affected their uptake of financial services. From the responses obtained, the respondents indicated that professional experience of the people offering financial literacy was questionable since some of them were not very clear with what they were sharing in terms of the financial literacy. They had noted that some of the professionals sent to them to educate them about the uptake of financial services could not answer some of their questions.

Collateral Requirement

The respondents were asked to what extent they agreed or disagreed to the opinion that collateral requirement affected their uptake of formal financial services. Their responses are shown in figure 4.12.

Table 2 Collateral Requirement on the Uptake of Financial Services

	1	2	3	4	5	Weighted Mean
1 Log books are accepted as collateral for Kajiado County SMEs to acquire financial credit	252	0	0	0	0	1
2 SMEs in Kajiado County use their bank accounts as collaterals for credit from financial institutions	45	167	5	0	35	2
3 Financial institutions in Kajiado County accept land title deeds as collateral for credit from financial institutions	53	13	136	46	4	3
4 SMEs in Kajiado County town guarantee one another as collateral for credit from financial institutions	0	3	69	165	15	3
5 We are able to provide collateral required by the financial institutions in Kajiado County	12	37	199	0	4	3

From the above data, the findings generated a mean of weighted means of 2 which implies that the respondents agreed to the opinion that indeed collateral requirement has an impact on the uptake of formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County. From the findings above, it is clear that log books are accepted as collateral for Kajiado County SMEs to acquire financial credit as strongly agreed upon by majority of the respondents who recorded a weighted mean of 1. It was also established by the researcher that many of the SMEs in Kajiado County use their bank accounts as collaterals for credit from financial institutions as evident from the respondents who realized a mean weight of 2. The question on whether financial institutions in Kajiado County accept land title deeds as collateral for credit from financial institutions received varying responses; however, majority disagreed with this particular opinion. This was evident from the mean weight of 3. Majority of the respondents also disagreed that they were able to provide collateral required by the financial institutions in Kajiado County. This was revealed from the weighted average of 3 exhibited from the respondents.

Besides, the respondents were asked to specify any other aspects on collateral requirements that they felt also affected the uptake of the formal financial services in Kajiado County. A good number of the respondents said that collateral requirement was a main hindrance for the access to financial services to help them uplift their businesses. They also mentioned of harassment for payment by the financial institution that lend them money. This as a result made them shy away from taking up the formal financial services.

Uptake of formal financial services by SME's in Kajiado County

The researcher also sought to establish the extent to which respondents were in agreement with certain variables relating to the uptake of formal financial services in Kajiado County. Table 4.14 presents the findings.

Table 3 Uptake of Formal Financial Services by SME's in Kajiado County

	1	2	3	4	5	Weighted Mean
Uptake of financial services in Kajiado						
1 County requires collateral	226	16	0	0	8	1
Financial literacy is required by SMEs						
2 Kajiado County to secure credit	63	158	9	14	2	2
Effective servicing of credit by SMEs in						
3 Kajiado amount to financial literacy	21	107	46	54	0	2
Conditions by financial institutions in Kajiado						
4 County favour SMEs in getting credit	32	36	56	121	6	3
SMEs in the area manage to adhere to the						
5 conditions by the institutions in the area	39	37	123	46	1	3

From the above data, the findings generated a mean of weighted means of 2 which implies that the respondents agreed to the opinion that indeed the uptake of formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County depends on a number of factors.

From these findings, the researcher deduced that the uptake of financial services in Kajiado County requires collateral. This was supported by majority of the respondents who were represented by the mean weight of 1. Majority of the respondents also agreed that financial literacy is required by SMEs Kajiado County to secure credit. This was represented by the mean weight of 2. It was also noted by the researcher that majority of the respondents agreed that effective servicing of credit by SMEs in Kajiado amount to financial literacy. This was represented by the mean weight of 2. In addition, the researcher discovered that conditions by financial institutions in Kajiado County did not favour SMEs in getting credit. A mean weight of 3 corresponded to the majority of the respondents. The respondents also disagreed that SME's in the area manage to adhere to the conditions by the institutions in the area and this was represented by a mean weight of 3.

Besides, the respondents were asked to specify any other aspects on uptake of formal financial services by SME's in Kajiado that were important. From the responses obtained, there was emphasis on strategies that motivate small and medium entrepreneurs to improve on productivity and investments and through these strategies, the entrepreneurs will feel appreciated thus enabling them to perform better.

Inferential Statistics

The study indicated that there was a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.834$, $p = 0.037$) between the level of financial literacy and the uptake of formal financial services by SME's in Kajiado County. The study further indicated that there was a very strong positive relationship between the collateral requirement and the uptake of the formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County ($r = 0.939$, $p = 0.001$). The correlation in this case was also significant. Table 4 shows that the 4 independent variables that were studied explain only 76.6% of the uptake of formal financial services by SME's in Kajiado County. This is indicated by the value of the adjusted R^2 . This therefore means that other factors not studied in this research contribute 23.4% of the uptake of formal financial services in Kajiado County. Thus, it is important that further research be conducted to investigate these factors. Table 4 shows that the significance value is 0.035 which is lower than 0.05 thus the model is statistically significant in predicting how the interest rates charged, level of financial literacy, collateral requirement and the number of lending institutions influence the uptake of formal financial services. The F critical at 5% level was also significant since $p < 0.05$. Thus, this tells us that the overall model was significant.

Table 4 Regression Coefficients for Variables

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		correlation	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	zero order
(Constant)	26.624	41.927	0.874	0.383		
Level of Financial literacy	1.357	1.116	0.064	1.216	0.035	0.028
Collateral Requirement	2.343	0.006	0.121	0.904	0.028	.176*
R Square	0.771					
Adjusted R Square	0.766					
Durbin-Watson	1.478					
F	1.11					
Sig.	0.35					

a. Dependent Variable: Uptake of formal financial services

The two independent variables were found to influence the uptake of formal financial services in Kajiado County with collateral requirement topping the list. This is evident from their p values which were less than 0.05. Collateral Requirement (0.028). This tells us that in Kajiado County, these two factors are major determinants for the uptake of formal financial services by the SME's. The study findings were that the level of financial literacy significantly affects the uptake of formal financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County. The study also found that making informed decisions by small entrepreneurs in Kajiado County is due to their financial literacy. This concurs with the findings of Muia and Otiende (2004), when they opined that education is a basic human right and a special tool for achieving the goals of equity in development and peace. It is crucial in changing the status of small entrepreneur's businesses transactions and improving their empowerment. In addition, the study also found out that the efficiency of managing finances by small and medium entrepreneurs amounts to financial literacy. This is according to King and McGrath (2006) that education is one of the factors that impact positively on growth of firms. Also, according to Namusonge (2005), it is entrepreneurial education and training that has been found to have a significance role in the stimulation of entrepreneurship and self-

employment among the micro, small and medium entrepreneurs. This has thus guided many SME's in making informed investment decisions.

Findings in this study indicate that collateral requirement is a major hindrance to access of financial services by the SME's in Kajiado County. It also revealed that log books are accepted as collateral for Kajiado County SMEs to acquire financial credit. This aspect is supported by Bowen et al. (2009), when they proposed that many SME's have turned out to use their assets as security when securing financial services from institutions. The study further revealed that many of the SME's are not able to provide for themselves the collateral required for them to secure the formal financial services. This could be due to aspects such as lack of sufficient information on financial literacy. This fact has been exemplified and supported by scholars such as Fletschner (2008a), when they contended small entrepreneurs are more likely to be credit constrained due to that lack of collateral than established ones of equivalent socio-economic conditions.

Conclusion And Recommendations

the study established that the level of financial literacy is very crucial for any SME to take up the formal financial services. This was a platform that would engage them on providing the relevant information that they needed before securing the services. This study recommends the following measures to both the SME's and the formal financial institutions providing the formal financial services. The main strategy of surviving SME's during this Century inevitably will be associated with the formation of sufficiently effective innovation management system for coping with emergent industries and aggressive innovative movement coming from competitors and the provision of adequate leadership skills for improving SME's responsive directions. Therefore, formal financial institutions should lay more emphasis on cutting down the high interest rates charged and the "harsh" collateral requirements that would otherwise permit large scale provision of financial services to the start-ups businesses and already established SME's. Research can also be carried out to establish the long-term sustainability of growth of SME's as a means of improving businesses performance.

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